

Strategy for the development of services in Uzbekistan in an innovative way (on the example of tourist services)

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Abstract

The article examines the possibilities of innovative development of the service sector in the country and its regions using the example of the tourism services market. The rating indicators for the provision of services in the regions of the country were also assessed.

Keywords: services, provision of services, travel services, tourist, innovative travel services, hotel, international tourist flow,

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Introduction

Despite the global changes that could negatively affect the development of tourism in the world economy, in particular, the crisis of the travel company Thomas Cook, the emergence of the UK exit from the European Union (Brexit), despite the decline in tourism development in Europe, the world It is possible to observe the development of the tourism industry on a large scale. According to the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), in 2019, the tourism services sector grew by 8.0 percent in the Middle East, 5 percent in Asia and the Pacific, 4 percent in Europe and Africa, and 2 percent in North and South America.¹ These trends provide a basis for the tourism industry to be assessed as a stable sector, despite various negative developments.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has been prioritizing reforms aimed at developing the tourism sector and further strengthening its role in the national economy. We must take comprehensive measures to develop tourism, attract investment and increase human resources, said the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev. Our tourism is often limited to our ancient cities, historical and cultural monuments. However, the unique nature of our country, national reserves, there is a great potential for the development of tourism in mountainous areas. In particular, the development of medical tourism, pilgrimage tourism and ecotourism will give a great impetus not only to the development of the economy, but also the social sphere. It is necessary to develop a national concept of tourism development in 2019-2025 and on this basis to increase the number of foreign tourists visiting our country in 2025 to 7 million, and the annual income from tourism exports to 2 billion US dollars.² The above views indicate that in recent years, the development of tourism has become one of the priorities of state socio-economic policy.

Setting a scientific problem

Uzbek economists E.V. Golisheva, N.S. Ibragimov, B.Sh. Safarov, T.T. Tashmurotov, D.K. Usmanova, O.M. Khamidov³ et al have conducted research on the peculiarities of the development of the market of tourist services in the

¹ Tourism development practice and current principles. 18.03.2020 y. <https://strategy.uz/index.php?news=874>

² Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. 28.12.2018 y. <http://www.xabar.uz/siyosat/president-shavkat-mirziyoyevning-oliy-majlisga-murojaatnomasi>

³ Golysheva E.V. Improvement of the organization and mechanism of regulation of tourism development in market conditions. Diss. ... Cand. econom. sciences. - Tashkent, 2012.– 156 p.; Ibragimov N.S. Application of the concept of destination management in the development of international tourism in Uzbekistan. I.f.n. diss. - Buxoro, 2006. - 183 p .; Safarov B.Sh. Methodological bases of innovative development of the national tourism services market. - T .: Science and technology, 2016. - 184 p .; Tashmurotov T.T. International tourism. - T .: Turon - Iqbol, 2007. – 320 p.; Usmanova D.K. Features of the formation of a tourist product and promising directions of its development. Diss. ... Cand. econom. sciences. - Samarkand: SamISI, 2009 .-- 157 p .; Khamidov O.M. The choice of the competitive strategy of the enterprise in the tourism services market of Uzbekistan. ... Diss. ... Cand. econom. sciences. - Samarkand: SamISI, 2006.– 155 p.

country, the direction of the organization of tourist services in a market economy, the improvement of management practices of enterprises and organizations engaged in tourism. Also, the theoretical and practical issues of the development of tourism in the country in an innovative way are systematized and not studied as a complex, as a special object of study.

Analysis of research on this issue in the economic literature highlights the need to improve the modern mechanism of public-private partnership to achieve such priorities as the transition of tourism services to innovative development in the context of economic modernization, including the formation of innovative tourism infrastructure, improving the country's international tourism competitiveness. produces. The urgency of the problem, the insufficient study of the economic literature, the scientific and practical significance of the expected scientific results led to the selection of this topic as an object of research.

The main results

In assessing the role of tourism in the country's economy, it is necessary to analyze the share of this sector in the country's GDP. The analysis shows that in 2014-2019, the share of tourism in the country's GDP increased as a result of consistent implementation of measures to strengthen the role of tourism in the economy of Georgia, Mexico, Armenia, Spain, Azerbaijan, Malaysia, China, Germany, Kazakhstan, Ukraine. In the Maldives, Turkey, Tajikistan and Uzbekistan, the opposite is true, ie the share of tourism in GDP has decreased (see Table 1).

According to the analysis of data presented in Table 1, in recent years it is expedient to develop innovative tourism based on modern technologies in the development of the tourism industry in our country. It is expedient to transfer the system of measures for the development of innovative tourism to the practice of providing "smart tourist services" by increasing the number of hotels in the country, in particular, the number of hotels, holiday homes for tourists, tourist bases. At the same time, we believe that the priorities of the program "The European Capital of Smart Tourism" put forward by the countries of the European Union should be used in the practice of our country. In particular, ensuring socio-economic and political stability in cities with high tourist flows, the creation of special conditions for people with disabilities, the digitization of tourism services with the help of modern information and communication technologies.

Table 1:
Trends in the share of tourism in the GDP of some countries⁴

	2014 y	2015 y	2016 y	2017 y	2018 y	2019 y
Maldives	80,4	84,5	74,5	74,8	76,2	76,6
Georgia	20,4	20,9	25,2	27,1	31,0	32,3
Mexica	14,8	14,9	15,7	15,9	16,0	16,3
Armenia	12,2	12,8	14,0	14,6	15,7	16,7
Spain	13,8	14,1	14,1	14,5	14,3	14,6
Azerbaijan	8,2	8,6	10,2	13,2	14,6	15,5
Malaysia	13,0	14,2	13,4	13,8	13,4	13,5
Turkey	12,2	12,2	12,0	11,1	11,6	11,7
China	9,6	10,0	10,5	11,1	11,6	11,6
Germany	10,4	10,6	10,7	10,7	10,7	10,9
Tajikistan	8,9	9,3	8,6	8,6	8,3	8,5
Kazakhstan	5,9	4,9	5,6	6,0	6,0	6,1
Ukraine	5,1	5,5	5,4	5,4	5,7	5,7
Russia	4,8	4,9	4,7	4,9	4,8	4,9
Uzbekistan	2,8	2,7	2,8	3,0	2,7	2,7

According to the analysis of official data, in 2016-2020, the number of tour operators serving tourists in the country increased by 1.6 times from 484 to 1,346. We can also observe that during the analyzed period, the number of tourist accommodation increased by 2.3 times from 750 to 1,308, and the number of places in them increased by 2.2 times, from 34.1 thousand to 61.5 thousand. In particular, in 2017-2019, the volume of exports of tourist services in the country increased 2.4 times, from 547 million US dollars to 1.3 billion US dollars.⁵

Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4095 "On measures to accelerate the development of the tourism industry" Acceleration of growth is aimed at attracting foreign direct investment in the development of the hotel industry in the country, and target parameters for the construction of hotels in the regions of the country in 2019-2021 have been adopted.⁶ Due to the developed target parameters, a state program has been adopted to increase

⁴ based on the data Tourism, total contribution to GDP (share,%) <https://knoema.ru/atlas/topics/%D0%A2%D1%83%D1%80%D0%B8%D0%B7%D0%BC/%D0%9E%D0%B1%D1%89%D0%B8%D0%B9-%D0%B2%D0%BA%D0%BB%D0%B0%D0%B4-%D1%82%D1%83%D1%80%D0%B8%D0%B7%D0%BC%D0%B0-%D0%B2-%D0%92%D0%92%D0%9F/%D0%9E%D0%B1%D1%89%D0%B8%D0%B9-%D0%B2%D0%BA%D0%BB%D0%B0%D0%B4-%D0%B2-%D0%92%D0%92%D0%9F-%D0%B4%D0%BE%D0%BB%D1%8F-percent>

⁵ Tourism Development in Uzbekistan: An Overview for 2016-2020. 17.05.2021 y. <https://review.uz/oz/post/razvitiie-turizma-v-uzbekistane-obzor-turotrasli-za-2016-2020-gg>

⁶ Annex 1 to the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4095 "On measures to accelerate the development of the tourism industry." 05.01.2019 y. <https://lex.uz/docs/4141452>

the total number of hotels in the country from 886 to 2,394 by 2018 by 2.7 times compared to 2018. It is also planned to increase the number of hotel rooms by 2.5 times from 19,832 to 50,044 (see Table 2).

Table 2:

Information on the situation before the implementation of the target parameters for the construction of hotels in Uzbekistan in 2019-2021⁷

	2018 y.		2021 y.	
	Number of hotels	Number of rooms	Number of hotels	Number of rooms
Republic of Uzbekistan	886	19 832	2 394	50 044
<i>including:</i>				
The Republic of Karakalpakstan	31	515	119	2 153
Andijon	18	507	82	1 586
Bukhara	160	2 139	369	6 071
Jizzakh	29	493	98	1 772
Kashkadarya	38	731	126	2 368
Navoi	20	499	72	1 485
Namangan	126	2 278	174	3 117
Samarkand	13	195	236	5 307
Syrdarya	33	785	100	2 100
Surkhandarya	33	739	56	1 123
Tashkent	48	1 181	152	3 106
Fergana	67	1 350	150	2 882
Khorezm	67	1 561	165	3 455
Tashkent c.	203	6 859	495	13 519

Based on the data in Table 2, the rating indicators on the number of hotels and the number of rooms in the regions of the country were developed. It was based on the difference between the total number of hotels in the country and the number of rooms in them from the regional average. According to the results of the calculation of the number of hotels, the rating of the number of hotels in Tashkent (2.8947), Bukhara (2.1579), Samarkand (1.3801) and Namangan (1.0175) regions compared to other regions of the country. is significantly higher. The analysis shows that the ratings of some regions of the country have decreased in 2018-2021. In particular, the rating of Tashkent city decreased from 3.2077 in 2018 to 2.8947 by 2021, in Bukhara region from 2.5282 to 1.6984, in Namangan region from 1.9910 to 1.0175 (see Figure 1). This is due to the growing number of newly built hotels in the country, a sharp

⁷ Annex 1 to the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4095 "On measures to accelerate the development of the tourism industry." 05.01.2019 y. <https://lex.uz/docs/4141452>

increase in the volume of hotel services in Samarkand, Tashkent, Kashkadarya, Syrdarya, Jizzakh, Andijan, Navoi regions and the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Figure 1. Rating indicators on the number of hotels in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan⁸

According to the analysis of data in Figure 1, in 2021, the rating indicators of the number of hotels in Surkhandarya (0.3275), Navoi (0.4211), Andijan (0.4795), Jizzakh (0.5731) and Syrdarya (0.5848) regions of the country significantly lower than in other regions.

⁸ Created by the author

Figure 2. Rating indicators on the level of capacity of hotel services in the regions of Uzbekistan⁹

We also calculated the results of the rating of the capacity of hotel services in the regions of the country in order to clarify the results of our research. According to the results of the calculations, the rating of Tashkent city (3.7820), Bukhara (1.6984), Samarkand (1.4847) regions is the highest in the country, while Surkhandarya (0.3142), Navoi (0.4154), Andijan (0.4437) and Jizzakh (0.4957) regions have significantly lower ratings (see Figure 2).

In order to draw concrete conclusions on the development of the tourism industry in our country, it is expedient to develop rating indicators of the above order. The final results of the rating indicators developed for the provision of hotel services for tourists in the country will be obtained by calculating the arithmetic mean of the sum of the results recorded by the regions in terms of the number of hotels and their capacity. The rating indicators for the provision of hotel services in the regions of the country are shown in Figure 3.

⁹ Created by the author

Figure 3. Rating indicators for the provision of hotel services for tourists in the regions of Uzbekistan, 2021¹⁰

Conclusions and suggestions

Based on the results of our research, we can say that the following results can be achieved through the implementation of the interregional rating of the types of services provided to tourists in our country by the above method:

- Determining the level of coverage of tourist services in the country, including in the regions, and the effectiveness of measures aimed at improving its quality;

- Analysis of the development indicators of tourism services by regions, in particular, to increase the efficiency of their tourism potential through the development of regional programs aimed at developing the provision of tourist services in underdeveloped regions;

- identification of existing problems of the country in the field of tourism and their timely elimination;

- identification of priorities of state programs aimed at the development of tourism in the long run, etc.

In our opinion, in the development of the tourism industry of our country in recent years, it is expedient to pay attention to the following:

- Improving the practice of providing recreational tourism services, taking into account the rich natural and climatic conditions of the country;

¹⁰ Created by the author

- Development of action plans for the organization of various entertainment programs for tourists, including travel in areas with long-standing cultural and historical sites;
- Increasing the participation of exhibition houses, business centers in the development of business tourism, including the holding of business forums in free economic zones established in the country;
- state support of travel agencies on the basis of stimulating the export of tourist services;
- Transferring the activities of organizations providing tourist services and travel agencies to the path of innovative development;
- expanding the range of tourist services and products, including the use of advanced innovative technologies to further improve their quality;
- increase the number of partner countries with a visa-free regime for foreign tourists;
- Establishment of joint innovative activities of travel agencies providing tourism services and deepening the process of mutual cooperation between the tourism infrastructure;
- Development of a national international tourism marketing program to promote the tourist potential of our country at the international level, to study the needs of foreign tourists in the use of tourist services, etc.

In our opinion, in recent years, on the basis of the above proposals, the country will increase the role of tourism in the economy of our country through the development of tourism services. It also guarantees the long-term sustainable development of the industry.

List of used literature

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